

The dry closure of the Almagrera tailings dam: detailed modelling, monitoring results and environmental aspects

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Abstract

The Aznalcóllar tailings dam failure moved the Spanish authorities to pay attention to tailings deposits. The Almagrera tailings dam holds one of the largest mining waste deposits in Andalucía. The dry closure of this dam has been detailed in this manuscript. Some serious difficulties had to be solved. Firstly, the dam had undergone up to five raisings before the closure operations started and this process had not been properly documented. Secondly, the reservoir water was contaminated by the toxic tailings placed several meters below and, due to the high acidity of this water, the geotechnical characterization of the tailings deposit has been really challenging. Thirdly, the definition of the model itself has been a complex task due to the consideration of many phases and different hypotheses. In the finite elements calculation, a constitutive model of perfect non-associated plasticity has been used for the dam and a soft soil creep model for the tailings. Next, it has been decided to decontaminate a close mine by placing its abandoned material –*Las Viñas* fill- on top of the tailings deposit inside the reservoir. This operation generated important settlements on the tailings deposit. These settlements had to be accelerated by placing drainage wells to avoid the cracking of the final cap. The safety factor during the dry closure operations under dynamic loading was insufficient and a compacted rockfill reinforcement had to be laid on the downstream slope of the dam. Very few papers describe a successful dry closure of a tailings dam as is done here.

Keywords

Dry closure· Tailings dam· Toxic deposit· Settlement· Safety factor· Drainage wells.

Résumé

La rupture du barrage de stériles d'Aznalcóllar a poussé les autorités espagnoles à prêter attention aux dépôts de résidus. Le barrage de stériles d'Almagrera abrite l'un des plus importants dépôts de déchets miniers d'Andalousie. La fermeture à sec de ce barrage est présentée dans ce manuscrit. Certaines difficultés sérieuses ont dû être résolues. Premièrement, le barrage avait connu jusqu'à cinq surélévations avant le début des opérations de fermeture et ce processus n'avait pas été correctement documenté. Deuxièmement, l'eau du réservoir a été contaminée par les résidus toxiques placés plusieurs mètres plus bas et, en raison de la forte acidité de cette eau, la caractérisation géotechnique du gisement de résidus a été très difficile. Troisièmement, la définition du modèle lui-même a été une tâche complexe en raison de la prise en compte de nombreuses phases et d'hypothèses différentes. Dans le calcul par des éléments finis (EF), un modèle constitutif de plasticité parfaite non associée a été introduit pour le barrage et un modèle visqueux pour les déchets miniers. Ensuite, il a été décidé de décontaminer une mine à proximité -Las Viñas- en plaçant son matériau abandonné au-dessus du dépôt de résidus à l'intérieur du réservoir. Cette opération a généré d'importants tassements sur le dépôt de résidus. Ces tassements ont dû être accélérés en plaçant des puits de drainage pour éviter la fissuration de la couverture finale. Le coefficient de sécurité (CS) à la fin des opérations de fermeture à sec sous chargement dynamique était insuffisant et des renforts d'enrochement compactés devaient être posés sur la pente aval. Pas beaucoup d'articles décrivent une fermeture à sec réussie d'un barrage de stériles comme cela est fait ici.

Mots clés

Fermeture à sec • Barrage de stériles • Dépôt toxique • Tassement • Coefficient de sécurité • Puits de drainage.

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Introduction

Sensitivity towards the safety of mineral waste deposits in Spain has increased in recent years, especially after the catastrophic failure of Los Frailes dam at Aznalcóllar (Seville). This failure released approximately 1.3 million cubic metres of fine pyrite tailings and 5.5 million cubic metres of tailings water into the nearby river systems (Alonso and Gens 2006a and b, Zabala and Alonso 2011). Gens and Alonso (2006) concluded that the dam slide occurred due to the progressive failure in a brittle and very impervious clay foundation. At present, in the current legislation, mining companies are required to submit a plan for mine closure in advance. However, due to lack of foresight in the previous regulations, the Spanish regional governments are today confronted with the problem of closing a large number of abandoned mines and tailings dams, as is the case of the Almagrera tailings dam.

The Almagrera site is located in the south west of Spain, in Huelva (Andalusia), near the village of Calañas, in the eastern part of the province, to the west and not very far from Aznalcóllar. The Almagrera dam contains tailings from the mine that was exploited by the company “Minas de Almagrera SA” between 1980 and 2002. Later, the mine and the dam were abandoned. During the use of the mine, the company extracted and processed polymetallic sulphides, producing concentrates of copper, zinc and lead by the flotation process. The pyrite resulting from this treatment was used for the production of sulphuric acid, Oleum 20 and pentahydrate. The situation prior to the closure was that the mine had been abandoned for quite a few years. The water accumulated in the reservoir was partially covering the tailings and was highly contaminated, due to the toxicity of the abandoned material. In addition, the safety factor (SF) of the dam did not fulfil the Spanish seismic regulations established at the time.

A project for the dry closure of the dam has been presented and partially executed. The project included drainage, water drawdown, reinforcing the dam, filling the reservoir with surrounding contaminated material and covering the tailings with a final cap. Some serious difficulties had to be solved during the closure. Many years had passed before the project started and most of the information was lost. The dam had been raised up to five times and the information about these operations had not been properly recorded.

Davies and Martin (2000) calculated that there are more than 3500 tailings dams worldwide. Yin et al. (2011) analysed the stability of a copper tailings dam in China. A laboratory physical model test was used for that purpose. Yin et al. (2012) studied the influence of seepage on the microstructure of tailings, concluding that it

is the main factor that damages tailings dams. Many papers have described the failures of tailings dams. According to Davies (2002) from two to five “major” tailings dam failures had occurred in the years before his paper. Rico et al. (2008a) made a thorough report of tailings dam failures in Europe. Van Niekerk and Viljoen (2005) described the causes and consequences of the Merriespruit dam (South Africa) failure. Rico et al. (2008b) compiled historic tailings dam failures with the idea of establishing correlations between tailing ponds geometric parameters and the hydraulic characteristics of the floods. Larrauri and Lall (2018) presented an updated statistical model to estimate the volume of released tailings and the maximum distance travelled by the tailings in the event of a tailings dam failure, based on physical parameters of the dams. Zandarín et al. (2009) studied a tailings dam located in Cuba. Their analysis was focused on the role of capillary water. The failure of the Mount Polley tailings dam in Canada, in 2014, was described by the Chief Inspector of Mines (2015) and Independent Expert Engineering Investigation and Review Panel (2015). The failure was due to the progressive rupture in the brittle clay foundation as in the Aznalcóllar dam. In 2015 the failure of two dams in Bento Rodrigues in Brasil released 62 million m³ of slurry. The latest failure reported (AGU 2017) is, for the moment, the partial collapse of the high wall of a reservoir at a phosphate factory, letting loose 100,000 cubic meters of highly acidic wastewater in the Ashalim riverbed (Israel).

All these data indicate that failures in tailings dams and their catastrophic consequences continue, so that precautions must be taken during the closure of these dams. By contrast, it should be highlighted that there are very few papers that show a successful dry closure of a tailings dam (v. Barnekow et al., 2003). Moreover, in this manuscript the solution to some interesting geotechnical problems is presented, including the constructive details and the calculation methods.

A short preliminary presentation of the model, based only upon the first site investigation and insisting mainly on the dynamic aspects, was carried out by Justo et al. (2013). The detail of the modelling, the new calculations and the environmental aspects are explained in the present article. The paper is structured as follows. In the site description section, the geology of the area and the dam prior to the closure operations are described. Next, the SF required for the dam according to the Spanish legislation is reported. In the methodology section, the eleven phases followed in the closure operations are described. Then, the finite element model to simulate the closure operations is described. This includes a description of the pseudo-static seismic input and the calculation of the SFs. Finally, the results are analysed and the main conclusions drawn are summarised.

Data

Geology

From a geological point of view, the area is included in a region called Faja Piritica (Pyrite Belt), one of the three parts into which the South-Portuguese zone is divided. It is the southernmost part of the European Variscan Belt. It covers a vast area about 250 km long, having a maximum width of 75 km. It is an exotic land accreted to the autochthonous Iberian Peninsula as a fold belt of southwest convergence and a low-medium metamorphic grade. The Iberian Pyrite Belt has sedimentary and igneous rocks of the late Devonian-Carboniferous age. There are three different litho-stratigraphic units (Schermerhom 1971). The oldest one, the PQ group, is composed of phyllites and quartzites from the Frasnian and late Famennian periods. This layer has a thickness of 2000 m. The Vulcan sedimentary complex is a complicated sequence of volcanic rocks interspersed with slate and chemical sediments. It was formed between the late Famennian and Viséan periods. The thickness of this layer is very variable and ranges between 0 and 1300 m. The youngest unit is the Culm group which is formed of slate and a turbidite sequence. It has a maximum height of 3000 m and dates from the later Viséan to the medium-later Pennsylvanian periods (Tornos, 2006). All these materials exhibit substantial variations in facies which, together with the Variscan deformation, present difficulties for the establishment of a detailed stratigraphic column. A part of the igneous facies, normally present, is of acidic nature (dacites and rhyolites) accompanied by basic basalts characterised by an important hydrothermal state of alteration. The Pyrite Belt is one of the most outstanding ore provinces of the world and probably hosts the largest concentration of volcanogenic massive sulphide deposits worldwide (Sáez et al 1999). More than 80 mineral deposits of sulphides and 300 of magnesium are located within it. This fact has produced an important mining activity in the area for thousands of years (Nocete et al. 2005).

The dam prior to the closure operations

Figure 1 shows an aerial view, taken in 2005, several years before the closure works started. The reservoir and the dam (running southwest to northeast) can be seen to the right of the picture. The dark colour of the reservoir corresponds to the underwater tailings. To the left, the tailings, exposed to the air, take on a grey colour.

Fig.1 Aerial view of the Almagrera site before closure (2005)

At the beginning of the project, a large portion of the toxic deposit was several meters underwater. The accumulated water was highly contaminated by the toxic tailings and reached 209 meters above sea level (Fig. 2).

The Almagrera tailings dam has a height of 37.3 m at its axis above the lowest foundation level. It has been raised up to five times adding material on the downstream slope. This slope was 1.7 (H): 1(V) in the first three risings and 2 (H): 1 (V) in the last two. The original axis and the situation of the dam after the last three risings can be observed in Fig.2. The dam is of a downstream borrow material type, with an upstream sloping core. Its foundation is formed by an alternation of volcanic and inter-stratified sedimentary rocks, including lava, clayey phyllite and shale. According to a report delivered before the 5th rising, the filter criterion to avoid fines migration was not fulfilled. Thus, the dam really behaved as a homogeneous dam. During the 5th rising, an inclined sand and gravel filter was placed between the 4th and 5th rising shells, fulfilling filter criteria, in addition to a downstream foot drain below it and the downstream shell. Leaks up to 16 m³/h appeared in the downstream slope.

	CLAY CORE. 5Th RAISING SC, $c=18$ kPa, $F=30^\circ$, $g=19.8$ kN/m ³ , $K=10^9$ m/s, $E=50$ MPa		
	SAND FILTER SP-SM, $c=1$ kPa, $F=35^\circ$, $g=20$ kN/m ³ , $K=10^9$ m/s, $E=50$ MPa		
	SELECTED ROCKFILL $c=1$ kPa, $F=35^\circ$, $g=20$ kN/m ³ , $K=5.1 \cdot 10^9$ m/s, $E=60$ MPa		
	CLAY CORE SC, $c=18$ kPa, $F=30^\circ$, $g=19.8$ kN/m ³ , $K=10^9$ m/s, $E=50$ MPa		
	WEATHERED ROCK SC, $c=50$ kPa, $F=20^\circ$, $g=20.5$ kN/m ³ , $K=1.4 \cdot 10^9$ m/s, $E=300$ MPa		
	"LAS VIÑAS" FILL $c=1$ kPa, $F=30^\circ$, $g=20$ kN/m ³ , $K=1.2 \cdot 10^9$ m/s, $E=10$ MPa		
B: BOREHOLE		I: INCLINOMETER (45 m)	
P: PIEZOMETER		E: EXTENSOMETER (45 m)	

Fig.2 Central cross-section of the Almagrera dam before closure.

Safety for tailings dams in the Spanish legislation

As the new Royal Decree 975/2009 (2009) on the treatment of tailings and protection and rehabilitation of the space affected by mining activities does not give specific instructions for safety, it was necessary to recur to the general instructions for dams (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente, 2011b).

Categories and SFs

In the security standard dictated by the Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente (2011a) for classification, dams and ponds are classified, depending on the potential damages derived from their hypothetical breakage, or their malfunction, in one of the following categories:

Category A: dams or ponds where breaking or malfunctioning can seriously affect urban centres or essential services, as well as producing very important material or environmental damages.

Category B: dams or ponds, whose breaking or malfunctioning may result in significant material or environmental damage or affect a small number of homes.

Category C: dams or ponds, whose breaking or malfunctioning may result in minor material damage and only incidentally loss of human life. In any case, this Category will include all dams and rafts not included in categories A or B.

Notwithstanding, the Royal Decree 975/2009 specifies the following conditions for a waste installation to be classified within category A:

- a) If, according to a risk assessment carried out taking into account factors such as the current or future size, location and environmental impact of the waste facility, a serious accident could result from a failure or malfunction, for example the collapse of a heap or the breakage of a dam.
- (b) If it contains wastes classified as dangerous under the Directive 91/689 / EEC above a certain threshold.
- (c) If it contains substances or preparations classified as dangerous under the Directives 67/548 / EEC or 1999/45 / EC above a certain threshold.

Three kinds of actions are considered according to their risk and persistence: normal actions, accidental actions and extreme actions. Normal actions are persistent actions: weight, hydrostatic pressure, pore water pressures and tailings pressure. Accidental actions are limited duration actions: e.g., rapid drawdown or earthquakes with a predictable intensity. Finally the actions are qualified as extreme when they only happen under extreme circumstances. Limit equilibrium (LE) methods and finite element (FE) methods are allowed for calculation. The minimal SFs are indicated in Table 1. When the model was carried out, a consulting enterprise classified the Almagrera dam in category C. Later studies (Álvarez-Valero et al. 2009) have reached the conclusion that “the supposed toxic spill would have a dramatic (environmental) impact, like the one that occurred in 1998 at Aznalcóllar, an abandoned mining site showing strong similarities with Almagrera”. This would mean that, according to this publication, it should have been included in category A. Later, when the results of the calculation will be examined, this matter will be treated anew.

Table 1 SFs required by the Spanish legislation (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente, 2011b).

Kind of action	Dam category	
	A or B	C
Normal	1.5	1.4
Accidental	1.3	1.2
Extreme	1.1	>1.0

Method

Closure phases

A mechanical model of all the operations involved during the closure was entrusted to the senior author. Most of them have been simulated in the model. This assignment was followed by a research project fostered by the Ministry of Science and Innovation of the Spanish Government. The closure of the Almagrera dam was planned according to the following phases:

1. First site investigation, as the reconnaissance made before construction was scarce. Many problems had to be solved to bore upstream (core perforation) and downstream boreholes.
2. Construction of lateral drainage channels to hinder the entrance of runoff and stream water into the reservoir.
3. Pumping of the reservoir toxic water, with the purpose of depurating it and sending it downstream.
4. Reinforcement of the dam during pumping, as the results of the model indicated that this was necessary.
5. Placement of coarse waste material removed from the Las Viñas mine on the tailings, inside the reservoir.
6. Monitoring.
7. Construction of special deep wells to accelerate the tailings settlements.
8. Second site investigation in the reservoir area by piezocones and boreholes.
9. Settlements calculation

10. Construction of the cap, when the remainder tailings settlement allows this.
11. Landscaping of the Las Viñas site, once the coarse toxic waste materials is removed.

Phase 1. First site investigation and geotechnical characterisation

As indicated under “Categories and safety factors”, the dam must fulfil certain conditions, among them SFs, at closure. Although some tests had been done by the mining company during the dam construction, these were not enough to assure an accurate calculation, and it was necessary to make boreholes and to carry out in situ and laboratory tests. Even the internal materials distribution inside the dam was not clearly established beforehand.

During 2008, five boreholes (27 to 47 m deep) were bored along each of three cross-sections, 50 m apart (Fig.3). Figure 2 shows the boreholes along the central cross-section. A similar distribution was chosen along the other two sections. In each section, one borehole was placed at the top of the dam, two were placed on the upstream slope and another two on the downstream slope. In situ permeability and geophysical tests were done inside the boreholes. The upstream boreholes were perforated from floating platforms on the very aggressive reservoir water. Some difficulties arose when the water height above the core was significant. A strong noise indicated that water was running at a high speed towards the rockfill placed below the core. The borehole was stopped and the hole was grouted. From this moment, the remaining upstream borehole was substituted by an inclined borehole perforated from the top (Fig. 2). In order to perforate the downstream boreholes, site paths were constructed on the slope with a bulldozer. This allowed taking the samples required for the analysis of the coarse grain size random materials in the quarry-run placed downstream. Large tailings samples were taken with a shovel (SS in Fig. 3). Several piezocone tests were carried out (CPTU-1 to CPTU-4 in Figure 3), but difficulties were encountered to place the machine during the tests in the very soft and deep tailings away from the shore of the reservoir. For this reason, only the upper tailings were duly investigated in this preliminary phase of soil investigation.

Fig. 3 Plan of the Almagrera reservoir showing the location of piezocones, borehole and shovel samples taken in this area.

CPTU-1 to CPTU-4 piezocones driven in 2008

CPTU-5 to CPTU-8 piezocones driven in 2010

CPTU-9 to CPTU-10 and 10bis piezocones driven in 2012

This first site investigation allowed the geotechnical characterisation of the dam. Table 2 shows the calculation parameters for the soil materials considered. As in this preliminary phase the investigation of the tailings was scarce, two hypotheses were considered with respect to this material: soft tailings and medium tailings.

According to the mining company, the density of the tailings was 1.61 g/cm³ and the main mineral was pyrite, with small quantities of other minerals.

Table 2 Materials and calculation parameters in the dam and tail of the reservoir (first site investigation)

Soil type	USCS	c' [kPa]	ϕ'	γ [kN/m ³]	k [m/s]	E [MPa]
Core	SC	18	30°	19.8	10 ⁻⁸	50
Filter	SP-SM	1	35°	20	10 ⁻⁵	50
Quarry run	GC	6	33°	20.2	6.5·10 ⁻⁵	30
Rockfill	SC	15	31°	21.9	9.5·10 ⁻⁷	60
Selected Rockfill		1	35°	20	5.1·10 ⁻³	60
Weathered Rock	SC	50	20°	20.5	1.4·10 ⁻⁶	300
Rock		250	20°	21.4	1.3·10 ⁻⁷	104
Soft tailings	ML	1	29°	13.2	5.1·10 ⁻⁹	0.52
Medium Tailings	ML	1	32°	19.7	5.1·10 ⁻¹⁰	1
<i>Las Viñas</i> material		1	30°	20	1.2·10 ⁻⁴	10

Phase 2.Perimeter drainage

Lateral drainage channels to hinder the entrance of runoff and stream water into the reservoir (Fig.4) were constructed in 2009.

Fig. 4 Lateral drainage channel covered with shotcrete (23rd of September 2009)

Phase 3.Pumping and depuration of the reservoir toxic water

Through pumping and drainage, the water level was lowered several meters to the level of the tailings. Fig.5 shows another aerial view taken in 2009, when this phase was quite advanced. The great mass of water which appeared in Fig.1 (2005) is no longer in the reservoir. Instead, the characteristic colours of the mining waste can be observed.

Fig. 5 Aerial view of the Almagrera site (2009)

Figure 6 shows the cracks opened on the tailings after pumping.

Fig. 6 Cracks in the tailings surface after pumping the reservoir water (23rd of September 2009)

Phase 4. Reinforcement of the dam

The SFs under seismic actions obtained with the parameters of the first site investigation did not fulfil the SFs specified in Table 1 (v. Justo, 2009). The reinforcement shown in Figure 7 was added to the dam on the downstream slope in order to fulfil this SF.

Fig. 7 The Almagrera closure reinforcement (13th of September 2010)

Phase 5. Placement of coarse waste material, removed from the Las Viñas mine

Several works were included in this phase:

- a) Pumping 653,000 m³ of coarse toxic waste material, from the *Las Viñas* mine, on the reservoir tailings.
- b) Levelling the surface and placing a 10 cm thick clayey layer on the top.
- c) In some places, where the machinery had difficulties to ride on the tailings, a geotextile was placed on the top.

Phase 6. Monitoring

One rod extensometer and one inclinometer, up to 45 m deep, were placed, in each section, at the top of the dam. Piezometric pipes were installed inside the boreholes at the crest of the dam and the top was closed to protect them (P1-1 to P3-1). Two vibrating wire piezometers (Fig. 2) were installed at the dam foundation in each of the three instrumented sections (P1-4, P1-5 to P3-4, P3-5).

Two vibrating wire piezometers (P1 and P2) were installed inside the reservoir once the fill had been placed (Fig.3).

Phase 7. Construction of special deep wells to accelerate the tailings settlements

The first author recommended prefabricated vertical drains in the hatched place in Figure 3, but the authorities preferred placing drainage wells and water extraction (Fig. 8). Surface and underground toxic water was

collected and taken to a passive treatment plant (Fig. 5). By November 2012, at the beginning of pumping, the head inside the wells ranged from 212 m, near the tail of the reservoir, to 204 m (the level of the top of the tailings) near the dam. In 2017, the head ranged from 209 m, near the tail of the reservoir, to 203 m near the dam.

Fig.8 Deep drainage well (13 September 2010)

Phase 8. Second site investigation in the reservoir area by piezocones and borehole

As stated in Phase 1, during the first site investigation, the tailings could not be duly tested owing to their low consistency that did not allow executing either borings or piezocones at the centre of the reservoir.

In September 2010, when level 208.77 was reached with the Las Viñas material, four piezocones (CPTU-5 to 8) were driven up to a depth exceeding sometimes 25 m. Later, in January 2012, three new piezocones were driven (CPTU-9, 10 and 10bis). A deep borehole (B-6) was drilled and laboratory tests were carried out. The detailed study of this new site investigation was carried out by Justo et al. (2014). The calculation parameters for the soils in the reservoir are shown in Tables 3 and 4. They are the mean of the values obtained from the piezocones and the borehole B-6.

It may be observed in Table 4 that, due to the presence of heavy metals, the density of the tailings is much higher than the values supplied by the mining company or the values introduced in Table 1, deduced from the first site investigation.

Table 3 Index and permeability coefficients in the reservoir area

Depth m	Soil type	<0.08 %	USCS	w _L	I _p	pH	w %	k _v m/s	k _h m/s	c _v m ² /s	c _h m ² /s
0-0.2	Silty clay	76.7	CL	39.7	18.3	3.5	8.6				
0.2-2.8	Levelling material	31.7	SM	28.7	8.8	5.5	29.3				
2.8-8.0	Las Viñas fill	59.8	CL- ML	26.1	4.3	3.9	23.3	5·10 ⁻⁷		4·10 ⁻⁶	
8.0- 25.0	Tailings up to 25 m	98.3	ML	NP	NP	5.5	12.4	7·10 ⁻⁸	3.3·10 ⁻⁸	1.8·10 ⁻⁶	2.1·10 ⁻⁵
25.0- 28.0	Tailings from 25 m						16.5	10 ⁻⁸	3.3·10 ⁻⁸	1.4·10 ⁻⁶	2.1·10 ⁻⁵
8.0- 28.0	Tailings (average)	98.3	ML	NP	NP	5.5	8.6	1.4·10 ⁻⁸	3.3·10 ⁻⁸	1.5·10 ⁻⁶	2.1·10 ⁻⁵
>28.0	Weathered rock										

Table 4 Strength and deformability parameters in the reservoir area

Depth m	Soil type	Undisturbed samples: blows/20cm	γ kN/m ³	c _u kPa	c' kPa	Φ' °	E MPa	E _{oed} MPa	C _c	C _s
0-0.2	Silty clay		20							
0.2-2.8	Levelling material	17	20		2	30°	13.6	18.3		
2.8-8.0	Las Viñas fill	43	22.3	108	32	26° 33°	12.6	17.0	0.15	0.024
8.0-25.0	Tailings up to 25 m		24.9		3.5	31°	2.0	2.7	0.16	0.013
25.0-28.0	Tailings from 25 m		31.1		11	31°	2.0	3.8	0.06	0.007
8.0-28.0	Tailings (average)		28.8	24	8.8	31° 35°	2.0	3.3		
>28.0	Weathered rock									

Phase 9. Settlements calculation

The settlements in the reservoir area were calculated using simple methods at the borehole B-6 location. The depth of the water table measured in the borehole (7 m) was assumed in the soil profile considered in the

analysis. Two calculations were carried out: the first using the oedometric moduli and the second with the values of C_c and C_s included in Tables 3 and 4. The results are displayed in Table 5.

A deeper settlements calculation was carried out using the FE method and will be presented later.

Table 5 Partial and total settlements (mm) calculated with two different parameters in the reservoir

Layer	Calculation parameter	
	E_{oed}	$C_c \& C_s$
Levelling material	4.3	4.3
Las Viñas up to 7m	25.4	15.4
Las Viñas 7-8 m	10	15.4
Tailings up to 25 m	1020	531.7
Tailings from 25 m	166.2	29.6
Total settlement	1265	596

Phase 10. Construction of the cap

This phase consists in laying the final cap. It has not yet been started because the remainder tailings settlements were still not allowable. This is due at the beginning of 2018. After the cap is in place, it is expected that the seepage of toxic water will decrease, but some discharge will remain and the treatment plant must remain there.

Phase 11. Landscaping of the Las Viñas site, once the coarse toxic waste materials are removed

This phase should be undertaken once the coarse toxic waste materials are removed, but this has not yet been done due to lack of funds

Final state

Figure 9 shows the present situation at the Almagrera tailings deposit and dam. The brown colour corresponding to the clay layer on top of the *Las Viñas* material can be observed. However, darker colours due to minerals can still be noticed to the right of the image. In addition, a row of drainage wells goes through the reservoir. Finally, the rockfill reinforcement can be observed to the right of the dam.

Fig. 9 Aerial view of the Almagrera site at 2013.

Figure 10 shows the final central cross-section of the dam. Some seepage of toxic water appears downstream of the dam and is pumped upstream to be depurated in the small treatment plant placed (now) upstream (Fig. 9).

Fig.10 Final central cross-section of the dam.

Modelling

Saad and Mitri (2011) indicated that the traditional approaches to consolidation, stability, and seepage analyses are inadequate for producing accurate and, in many situations, correct design and evaluation of these facilities. Instead, transient coupled nonlinear finite-element analyses must be carried out to investigate the hydromechanical behaviour of these facilities during its staged construction. The same may be applied to the closure operations as it has been made here.

Simulation of closure operations

The simulation of the closure operations has been carried out using a Finite Element (FE) model and the software Plaxis 2D v9.02. Triangular 15-nodes elements have been used. To simulate the behaviour of the dam, a Mohr-Coulomb model has been used. This is a model of perfect, non-associated plasticity. This same model was adopted by Gens and Alonso (2006) for the FE calculation of the Aznalcóllar dam. The tailings have been simulated with a soft soil creep model, more adequate for compressible soft soils. The characteristics of both material models were described by Brinkgreve et al. (2016).

The simulation of the closure operations included the following phases:

1. Initial phase (30/05/08). The layers of the *Las Viñas* fill were deactivated. The initial water level (209 m) was introduced. Gravity loading: the weight has been applied to the soil. Drained behaviour was assumed for the materials. Two hypotheses were considered:

- a) A phreatic ground water pressure was assumed using the water levels measured in the boreholes
- b) The ground water levels measured in the boreholes was used for a preliminary water level, but a steady state ground water flow has been calculated from this

2. Drawdown. Two hypotheses were considered as well:

- a) Drained behaviour for the materials and a phreatic ground water pressure were assumed using the water levels measured in the boreholes
- b) The materials were considered undrained and a fully-coupled flow deformation calculation was performed

It is not expected that both hypotheses would lead to identical results. The assumption of a phreatic ground water pressure (hypothesis a) is inaccurate. Hypothesis b is theoretically correct, but it is difficult to obtain

exact values of the permeability coefficients in the different dam materials. The best that might be expected is for both hypotheses to lead to acceptable results. The drawdown has been carried out in two phases:

2.1. Partial drawdown to the level 207.5 m (16/09/08) during 109 days. The initial water table measured the 30th May 2008 was introduced.

2.2. Total drawdown up to the level 204 on 23rd December 2009 during 463 days.

3. The reinforcement was applied between both drawdowns. The reinforcement elements were activated. A plastic calculation was carried out.

4. The Las Viñas fill was applied from: 23rd December 2009 to 23rd September 2011 (639 days). The corresponding layers were activated. From now on a consolidation calculation was carried out.

5. The levelling layer was applied in 366 days. The corresponding layer was activated.

6. Wells pumping during 641 days. A phreatic ground water pressure was assumed using the measured water levels in the boreholes and wells.

7. Long term stability. A time interval of 10^4 days was supposed.

8. Pseudo-static seismic calculations.

Pseudo-static seismic input

The Spanish standard for seismic calculations NCSR-02 (Ministerio de Fomento, 2002) considers large dams as constructions of special importance, and the Almagrera dam is included in this group. The site (the village of Calañas) has a seismic basic acceleration $a_b/g=0.08$.

The design acceleration will be:

$$a_d = S \cdot \rho \cdot a_b \quad (1)$$

where:

ρ = nondimensional seismic risk coefficient, function of the probability of a_d being exceeded, in a life period t of the structure = 100 years for especially important structures

S = coefficient of ground amplification

For $0.1 < \rho \cdot a_b$ (0.104 g) < 0.4 g:

$$S = \frac{c}{1.25} + 3.33 \left(\rho \frac{a_b}{g} - 0.1 \right) \left(1 - \frac{c}{1.25} \right) \quad (2)$$

where C is the ground coefficient, which takes the value of 1.0 for a V_s value of 1840 m/s and ground type I.

Substituting the corresponding values:

$$S=0.803$$

$$a_d = S \cdot \rho \cdot a_b = 0.08 \text{ g} \quad (3)$$

The Comité Nacional Español de Grandes Presas (1999) recommends for dams of category C a return period of 1000 years (v. ICOLD 2013) and a design acceleration:

$$a_d = 1.3 \quad a_b = 0.104 \text{ g} \quad (4)$$

This design acceleration was adopted in the model. This same design acceleration was applied for the *design earthquake* in dams of category A. For category A dams, the Spanish regulation considers as well an extreme earthquake, regarded as an extreme action, with design acceleration:

$$a_d = 2 \quad a_b = 0.16 \text{ g} \quad (5)$$

Safety factors. The strength reduction method

The SF was calculated using the shear strength reduction method (SRM). In this method the strength parameters $\tan \Phi$ and c are successively reduced until failure occurs. According to Zienkiewicz et al. (1975) this method yields a lower value of the SF obtained than methods based on limiting equilibrium (LE) solutions. Brinkgreve and Bakker (1991) indicated that “when further reduction of the strength parameters is not possible anymore, the construction has collapsed and the SF is obtained”; the procedure is made robust by adding an arc-length technique (v. Brinkgreve et al., 2016). They concluded that determination of the SF by means of SRM gives results that agree well with those from Bishop’s slip circle method. Griffiths et al. (1999) chose the non-convergence of the solution as a suitable indicator of failure; the limit equilibrium and FE factors of safety values were in close agreement. Dawson et al. (1999) obtained slightly larger SFs with SRM than those obtained with a log-spiral solution in homogeneous soils. Cheng et al. (2007) analysed the results obtained by a number of researchers and concluded that, in general, the SRM and LE methods give similar values of the SF. Sitharam and Hedge (2017) also reported that the SFs calculated from LE methods and SRM were found to be in good agreement.

In Brinkgreve et al. (2016), the total multiplier ΣMsf was used to define the value of the soil strength parameters at a given stage in the analysis:

$$\Sigma Msf = \frac{\tan\phi_{input}}{\tan\phi_{reduced}} = \frac{c_{input}}{c_{reduced}} \quad (6)$$

where the strength parameters with the subscript ‘input’ refer to the properties entered in the material sets and parameters with the subscript ‘reduced’ refer to the reduced values used in the analysis. ΣMsf is set to 1 at the start of a calculation to set all material strength to their unreduced value. When failure occurs the SF is given by:

$$SF = \frac{\text{available strength}}{\text{strength at failure}} = \text{value of } \Sigma Msf \text{ at failure} \quad (7)$$

The values of ΣMsf are drawn as a function of the displacements at some point. This curve reaches a maximum and then goes down to a stable value. Up to the maximum there has been convergence of the solution and further there is non-convergence, so that according to the criterion of Griffiths and Lane (1999) this maximum would correspond to the SF. However, Plaxis chooses the safety factor from the lower stable value, indicating that *this will ensure that with this approach failure has definitely occurred and no further reduction is possible, which is the proper moment to check the safety factors.*

When using *SRM* with advanced soil models, these models will actually behave like a standard Mohr-Coulomb model, since stress-dependent behaviour and hardening effects are excluded. The stress-dependent stiffness modulus (where this is specified in the standard model) at the end of the previous step is used as a constant stiffness modulus during the *SRM* calculation.

Results

Results of the FE calculations

Table 6 shows the safety factors (SFs), the maximum settlement at the top of the dam and the maximum settlement of the tailings. As stated under “Simulation of closure operations” two hypotheses have been considered:

- a) A phreatic ground water pressure was assumed using the measured water levels in the boreholes
- b) The measured ground water levels in the boreholes were used for a preliminary water level, but either a steady state ground water flow (for the initial high water level) or a fully coupled flow deformation (for drawdowns) was calculated from it.

When new layers were added (Viñas or levelling materials) or for long term calculations, consolidation calculations were carried out.

Safety factors

In the pseudo-static calculations the acceleration of 0.104 g was tried with positive or negative signs, and the smaller SF has been included in Table 6.

Table 6 SFs, settlements at the top of the dam, and maxima tailings settlements at the end of the different closure phases

Phase	Time (days)	Hypothesis <i>a</i>				Hypothesis <i>b</i>			
		SFs		Static settlement at top (mm)	Maximum tailings settlement (m)	SFs		Static settlement at top (mm)	Maximum tailings settlement (m)
		Static	Pseudo-static			Static	Pseudo-static		
High reservoir	0	1.44(1.41)	1.44(1.40)			1.51(1.43)	1.74(1.59)		
1st drawdown	109	1.52(1.44)	1.15(1.10)	21.6	0.34	1.50(1.44)	1.03(1.02)	-2.77	0.30
Reinforcement	109	1.97(1.63)	1.16(1.10)	21.6	0.34	1.96(1.50)	1.48(1.01)	-2.87	0.30
2nd drawdown	572	1.96(1.60)	1.34(1.25)	30.7	0.35	1.98(1.47)	1.98(1.11)	-0.83	0.47
Viñas	1211	1.95(1.77)	2.75(1.41)	43.3	1.03	1.97(1.77)	2.77(1.41)	6.30	1.02
Levelling layer	1577	1.98(1.77)	1.98(1.77)	52.4	1.29	1.95(1.77)	2.71(1.40)	14.00	1.29
Wells pumping	2218	1.94(1.76)	2.74(1.76)	52.5	1.41	1.95(1.77)	1.95(1.40)	14.00	1.41
Long term	12218	1.96(1.77)	2.74(1.40)	52.3	1.61	1.95(1.77)	1.95(1.40)	14.00	1.61
Long term extreme	12218	1.96(1.77)	1.32(1.25)	55.0	1.73	1.95(1.77)	1.31(1.24)	19.00	1.74
Long term design earthquake	12218			55.1	1.58			17.00	1.68

Inside brackets, SF corresponding to the lower stable value according to Plaxis

We shall mainly refer to the SFs corresponding to the maximum ΣMsf value although we shall comment, sometimes, on the values corresponding to the stable ΣMsf value.

The calculated static SFs were quite similar using both *a* or *b* methods indicated above. The smaller SF (1.44) corresponded to hypothesis *a* and the initial conditions and was in compliance with the code requirements for a category C dam (Table 1), but already after the first drawdown, the SF raised reaching values over 1.5, which is the required value for a category A dam under normal actions. The presence of the reinforcement produced an important increase in the SF while all subsequent operations produced only very small variations in it. Once the Viñas material was placed on the tailings, the SF was acceptable for a category A dam under normal actions using any definition of the SF.

Under pseudo-static conditions, there was a large decrease in the calculated SF after the first drawdown, due to the persistence of active interstitial pressures after dewatering. Fig. 11 shows the plastic points: some are internal, inside the complex dam-tailings, but the accumulation of plastic points along the downstream slope suggests the convenience of placing a reinforcement downstream to avoid a landslide of this slope. This instability was definitively corrected with the placement of materials on the tailings, and from this moment on, the SF was acceptable for a category A dam under accidental or even extreme actions using any definition of the SF. The materials placed on the tailings hinder any upstream landslide.

Fig. 11 Plastic points after the 1st drawdown for the *design earthquake*. Hypothesis *a*

Settlements at the top of the dam

With hypothesis *a*, the calculated settlement at the top of the dam is 21.6 mm after the first drawdown and increases up to 52 mm in the long term. The seismic acceleration produces very small changes in this settlement.

Under hypothesis *b*, the calculated displacements at the top are directed upwards (less than 3 mm) up to the second drawdown. With the placement of the Viñas material, the displacements change direction up to a maximum settlement of 14 mm in the long term. The seismic acceleration produced an additional settlement of 3 mm.

The explanation of these differences is that under hypothesis *a* the pore pressures in the dam are smaller.

Maximum settlement at tailings

The calculated tailings settlements were quite similar under hypotheses *a* and *b*. They increased sharply with the placement of the Viñas layers, when new weight was added to the tailings, reaching a maximum of 1.6 m in the long term. They were larger than those calculated with simpler methods (Table 5), as it must be taken into account that the FE calculation corresponds to the maximum tailings settlement and the calculations displayed in Table 5 correspond to the position borehole B-6 (Fig. 4). The seismic acceleration produced an additional displacement of only a few centimetres.

In November 2017, depressed zones were observed at the surface of the fill, where the thickness of tailings and fill were greater (Fig. 3).

Results of the monitoring

Figure 12 shows the evolution of the piezometric heads for the two piezometers placed at the upstream foot of the dam, inside the sludge (v. Fig. 3).

Fig. 12 Evolution of head measured at piezometers inside the tailings

Before installing the piezometers, on the 14th of September 2010, when the placement of the Viñas material was almost finished and the reservoir pumping had ended, the average piezometric head during the perforation of the piezocones (second site investigation) corresponded to the level 205.73. These piezometers were placed on 1st of August 2011. The readings of the piezometers reached the maximum on the 19th of September 2011 (head 204.92), near the end of Viñas fill placement (Fig. 12). The minimum head (201.95) was reached on the 5th of October 2012, at the end of wells pumping. Up to this moment there was a decrease in the head of 3.78 m, and from this moment on there were oscillations and a certain rise due to the intermittency of the pumping. The final head (18th of December 2013) was below the top of the tailings (\approx level 204). The movements of inclinometers and extensometers, located inside the dam were negligible, so it can be inferred that the dam was not very affected by the closure process.

With respect to the piezometers placed at the dam foundation in Sections 1 to 3, there was an increase in the water head from 0.5 up to 4 m with the placement of the Viñas material followed by a decrease of the same amount and stabilisation afterwards.

Conclusions

The paper details the operations carried out up to now for the dry closure of the Almagrera tailings dam. The difficulties encountered for the site investigation of the dam and the tailings have been presented. The methodology employed for the characterisation and modelling of the tailings has been fully explained. The survey of the monitoring at the end of each phase has guaranteed success in the following phase. A rockfill reinforcement had to be placed in order to stabilise the downstream slope. The closure operations included the

decontamination of a close mine by placing 653,000 m³ of compacted, coarse, toxic waste material on top of the tailings deposit inside the reservoir. This material stabilised the upstream slope.

Closure is being executed in 11 phases. The former 9 phases have successfully ended, but the last two have been stopped at the moment owing to cost problems. The variation of the SFs during the phases constructed has been detailed. The dam has been checked even under extreme actions. The settlements in the dam have nearly ended. Settlements from 17 to 27 cm are still likely to occur on the tailings.

Future research includes a more advanced simulation of the dam behaviour under seismic load conditions through a true dynamic calculation.

Acknowledgements

The help provided by the Instituto Universitario de la Construcción y Arquitectura for revising the English is acknowledged.

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